

Effectiveness of Video Materials in Teaching EFL Learners

Maxfuza Azimova¹ [orcid: 0009-0008-2362-8673](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2362-8673)
e-mail: maxfuzaazimova@utas.uz

Shoira Khanbabaeva² [orcid: 0009-0008-2362-8673](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2362-8673)
e-mail: shairaxan2015@gmail.com

Bakhrom Urolov³ [orcid: 0009-0002-2853-0479](https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2853-0479)
e-mail: oralovbahrom@gmail.com

¹Senior teacher, Department of Foreign language and literature, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent, 100149, Uzbekistan

²Senior teacher, Department of Foreign language and literature, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent, 100149, Uzbekistan

³Teacher, Department of Foreign language and literature, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent, 100149, Uzbekistan

Abstract: The current article is dedicated to the topic “Effectiveness of video materials in teaching EFL learners”. This article is described educational videos have become an important part of higher education, providing an important content-delivery tool in many flipped, blended, and online classes. Effective use of video as an educational tool is enhanced when instructors consider three elements: how to manage cognitive load of the video; how to maximize student engagement with the video; and how to promote active learning from the video. Video is a powerful tool in today's classroom. The success of teaching a foreign language through video depends on preparing students for the perception of a video. The expansion of international relations and the entry into our market of British and American teaching and methodical complexes, including video fragments, video lessons, significantly expanded our possibilities in using audiovisual techniques.

Key words: Dynamic ,subtitle, stimulate, versatility, sensory, utterances, engagement, facilitating, dimming, visibility, captions, blending learning.

1 Introduction

In the era of modern English language teaching when the focus has been on the communicative needs and interests of the students, teachers have to think of different innovations to bring to the classroom. As a consequence of the status of English language as the international language, the emphasis has been on the speaking and listening as two essential skills in communicating among people all over the world. The ever-growing needs of the listening and speaking skills has shifted the emphasis from learning the grammar and literature of the language to the communicative needs and skills. Thus, empowering the communication skills requires mastering the speaking and listening skills which are considered as the foundation of the language that facilitates the learning of other skills. No doubt that the communicative language teaching (CLT) is the most effective approach in this respect[1]. Accordingly, maintaining the communicative approach in English language learning requires many issues to be considered by course designers and teachers such as course design, classroom methodology, materials design, assessment, and the like. Due to the complexity and difficulty of the speaking and listening because of the associating skills and elements it is important to think of any motivating and effective strategies that help support and stimulate students' learning. Among these effective strategies are videos, films, and TV shows . In comparison to the textbooks and other traditional materials that might fail to adapt to students' needs and interests, video materials have got a great level of interest as they bring authenticity, reality, flexibility, and variety to the EFL classroom and curriculum development [2].

Several empirical research studies have proved the usefulness and the impact of multimedia on people in various fields such as policy, health, economy, and education is no exception. The literature on foreign language materials design and several empirical studies emphasized the importance of utilizing movies in EFL teaching on the basis of enhancing students' communicative skills and competence. Multimedia plays a great role in the improvement of English language proficiency. Video materials have been widely used in

EFL classroom because of their association with the communicative language teaching in addition to their role in facilitating language learning and stimulating the students [3].

In an attempt to enhance the speaking and listening skills several teachers decided to integrate video materials into classroom teaching for teaching a variety of subjects. Although some of them are concerned about teaching subjects such as writing, reading, Grammar, and listening, they use videos along with textbooks, worksheets, and other materials. They believe that the speaking skill is very challenging as it takes place in an EFL environment where there is a lack of exposure to the natural use of the language and a limited practice of the English language. In this respect, teachers have a role in designing, contextualizing, and adapting materials in accordance with the needs and interests of students. The main purpose of the study is to contribute to knowledge about designing and using video materials by teachers. For this, the study aims to gain an in-depth understanding of the utilization of video materials in EFL classroom, and exploring the reason(s) of incorporating video materials into the EFL classroom from the perspectives of teachers and students.

To put it in another way, the main focus has been on understanding or examining the role of video materials on a particular subject that might be speaking, listening, reading comprehensions, writing, or grammar. However, this study attempts to understand and examine the idea of integrating video materials in all kinds of subjects including speaking, listening, reading, writing, and grammar. To my knowledge, there is no study in the existing literature that has been conducted for this purpose.

2 Methods and materials

The success of teaching a foreign language through video depends on preparing students for the perception of a video. The expansion of international relations and the entry into our market of British and American teaching and methodical complexes, including video fragments, video lessons, significantly expanded our possibilities in using audiovisual techniques. In the event that the video is an attachment to a British or American educational complex, the teacher can use the technology of its application developed by foreign methods and described in teacher's book. In this case, video is an effective means of teaching a foreign language. Together with the English educational complexes there is a large number of feature films. Their viewing at the senior stage of education is close in importance to the reading of the original fiction and has no less significance for the study of a foreign language, since it allows to develop skills of listening, speaking and writing on authentic material, which contributes to the improvement of the communicative competence of students. We now have more access than ever to video. News programs, adverts, comedies, documentaries, dramas, academic lectures are available in digital format via the internet. Most of these resources weren't originally created as teaching materials. So it serves a real-world communicative purpose. Some materials are authentic resources adapted for language teaching. Authentic material not originally produced for ELT purposes, but adapted to different grades [4].

There are some positive characteristics of using video in the process of learning foreign languages: the class does not require dimming, and therefore, the contact of teacher with learners is continuous; video provides the possibility of using different modes of operation, e.g. freeze frame, using only video track (with audio track turned off) etc.; videos can easily be used for different types of work: individual, pair, group, collective; video equipment allows to split movie into desired number of clips, depending on the objectives of individual needs and characteristics of learners to continue working with each clip separately.

When teaching the perception of speech by ear, it is necessary, first of all, to develop aural skills and speech hearing with the support of native speakers. And in this case, it is the authentic audio video texts that allow the students to hear the speech of the native speakers, which reflects the living reality, the peculiarities of the national culture. Most importantly, the authentic material provokes the students' cognitive interest, the willingness to discuss problems, and, therefore, contributes to their motivation to learn a foreign language. If the learner perceives foreign speech, then he begins to realize that all his efforts spent on learning a foreign language were not in vain. Thus, the main task of the teacher at the stage of work with authentic material is the selection of audio or video material that would be interesting, informative, accessible to understanding, corresponded to the modern reality of a foreign language society and would create favorable conditions for mastering new regional information, behavior of native speakers, would facilitate their familiarity with the people's way of life, its culture.

Some teachers think that watching videos in EFL classroom is more entertainment than education. However, if we consider video as a text (a source of information) and we make a lesson using it that helps learners develop language; we can use video resources to capture learners' attention. Video materials should be accompanied with support for language learning.

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The simplest form of control is the task of specifying correct and incorrect statements, choosing one correct variant from several proposed. This form of control is the quickest way to test understanding when developing listening skills; however, it does not develop the ability to speak. Answers to the questions asked before the survey allows you to organize a conversation on the content of the scanned fragment, and at a more advanced stage - the discussion, especially when the questions are of a problem nature.

Arrangement of frames in the order of their appearance in the film allows not only check the attention of students, but they give support for oral utterances. Personnel illustrate the development of the plot and serve as a good basis for retelling. A more complicated task can be given to justify the choice, why one frame does not precede another. An even more complicated version is a method of introducing "jamming". When among the frames of this video fragment there is a frame from the "alien" film. Students are asked to explain why this shot could not be part of the video they watched.

The video serves as a good dynamic visibility for the practice of speaking in another language and creating situations of such communication in the classroom [7].

3 Result and Discussion

Teachers can use videos to deliver course information that can be extremely helpful in opening up class time. Lectures and other introductory information can be viewed before class, which allows for more practice- and skill-related class activities. These videos are accessible at the student's convenience and can be watched numerous times to assist with coursework and skill mastery.

Videos can be a great way to keep former students involved and engaged in what's going on at their alma mater. Alumni can watch athletic events, see campus activities and accomplishments and even take online courses. This can be a powerful recruitment tool, too! Alumni who feel engaged and informed about the current status of their alma mater will be much more likely to recommend it to potential students than those who don't.

Benefits of Using Videos in the Classroom

The benefits of using videos in an educational setting are numerous. Their convenience and versatility make them an asset to students, teachers and educational institutions alike.

Benefits to students:

Videos increase knowledge retention, since they can be stopped and replayed as many times as needed. They can also be reviewed long after the initial lesson was taught.

Benefits to teachers:

Videos increase student engagement, which in turn helps boost achievement. If students are interested in the material, they will better process and remember it.

They offer the flexibility to pause or skip throughout the video to have class discussions or review particular areas.

They enable teachers to create a flipped classroom, or “blended” learning environment. However, videos are also beneficial to teachers who teach in traditional classroom settings.

Benefits to institutions:

The potential to improve marketing and communications. Digital videos help to broaden your audience by reaching a greater number of people. These can be posted on your institution’s website or linked in an email or digital advertisement, or posted on social media. More flexible faculty and staff training. It’s often difficult for schools to assemble their faculty and staff at the same time, resulting in fragmented information acquisition. Using digital videos as a delivery method for training ensures that your faculty and staff have equal access to the information. Offering this option not only improves their retention and recall, but also serves as an archive to review it any time.

Ability to record campus events for live or on-demand viewing. When parents, students and alumni feel closer to what’s going on at your school, they’ll feel more invested, thus increasing the likelihood of positive recommendations and engagement with students new and old.

The following recommendations are helpful when creating an effective and beneficial educational video:

Limit videos to about five minutes or less, unless you are trying to relay a great deal of information. Maintain a conversational and enthusiastic tone to keep learners engaged. Properly balance auditory and visual elements throughout. Break videos into short segments by topic or theme. Include interactive and responsive features, such as a short quiz, to promote reflection and ownership. When using video clips in the classroom, shorter clips (around five to 10 minutes) help students learn the information without being overloaded or losing their focus. Longer videos are also effective — however, their total length should typically be limited to no more than 30 minutes. Showing video clips in short segments and keeping the total length contained to a concise running time helps to keep viewers engaged. Video brings the outside world into the classroom.

We now have more access than ever to video. Newscasts, advertisements, comedy routines, documentaries, dramas, and even academic lectures are available on DVD, via the internet, or even as student-produced projects. Most of what’s out there wasn’t originally produced as teaching material, which means it serves an authentic real-world communicative purpose. Some materials, for example the Discovery Channel documentary videos that accompany Cambridge University Press’s new Unlock series, are authentic materials adapted for language teaching. This is the best of both worlds: authentic subject matter not originally produced as ELT material, but later adapted to be pedagogically sound through grading.

Video engages learners

Some teachers feel that watching a video is entertainment rather than education. However, if we think of a video as a text – a source of information – and we create a lesson around it that helps learners develop language, then we can use video to capture and hold learners’ attention, while at the same time teaching them. Most of us wouldn’t give our learners any sort of text to read without offering support for language learning. When we offer the same support with video, the result will be effective, enjoyable lessons. (In future posts, I’ll explore ideas for exactly what to do with video in the classroom.)

Video is a great source of information

English learners – especially students of English for academic purposes – often need to carry out research for projects. Film and video (documentaries in particular) can be excellent sources of information. The visual input often helps clarify and support the language input, making research more effective.

It works at lower levels, too. In many cases, we can completely ignore the audio portion of a video and still be left with a great source of visual information. This is especially useful when we want to control the language level; we don’t need to grade the input, but instead can grade the language activities we provide. Academic skills such as summarising, paraphrasing, and giving an opinion are often linked with reading as a source of input. However, as I mentioned earlier, a video is also an information-rich ‘text’ that can provide students with the ideas and concepts that they must learn to manipulate successfully. Many teachers successfully use video in the ‘flipped’ classroom, where learners are given input (for example a YouTube video) outside of the classroom to feed into output, which can be done during class time.

Video can also provide a good reference point for critical thinking: for example, in considering advertisements, learners can develop the skills of considering motivation, whether or not supporting details are valid, and so on. Video provides a good model for learner output

Video may provide a significant means to improve student learning and enhance student engagement in biology courses. To maximize the benefit from educational videos, however, it is important to keep in mind the three key components of cognitive load, elements that impact engagement, and elements that promote active learning. Luckily, consideration of these elements converges on a few recommendations:

- Keep videos brief and targeted on learning goals.

- Use audio and visual elements to convey appropriate parts of an explanation; consider how to make these elements complementary rather than redundant.
- Use signaling to highlight important ideas or concepts.
- Use a conversational, enthusiastic style to enhance engagement.
- Embed videos in a context of active learning by using guiding questions, interactive elements, or associated homework assignments.

This method helped the learners to develop their listening skills. To develop sequencing, listening, and creative writing skills, we told students to play an excerpt of three to four minutes from the middle section of a work they have not yet studied in class. Depending on the class's achievement level, grade, course, and past experiences in literature, they may also be able to use an obscure excerpt from the middle section of a work already studied. Use of a familiar work will give this strategy an additional edge and provide the students with an evaluative tool for measuring their own comprehension and recall of previously studied literary works.

We used the materials, which we had used during my tutorial classes. The pupils were delighted with the change from their textbook. However, we found out that they were not used to such kind of new method. Their knowledge background was not as it should have been in most cases; they made many mistakes. Most of the pupils also liked the topics we had chosen.

4 Conclusions

The practical part is based on the practical use of audio materials in teaching which deals with the author's personal experience with using these materials in his lessons surveys. EFL classes with access to the necessary technology can effectively use YouTube and other online video streams. However, it is important to understand that there are some limitations. First, YouTube limits itself to copyright restrictions. If students are determined to focus on certain clips that are not available on YouTube because of copyright laws, then students will have to purchase these clips on their own. Secondly, given the vastness of the YouTube library, it may take some degree of structuring and guidance from the teacher to prevent students from spending unproductive hours on site viewing. The third attention of the teacher may have to be taken into account; this is the nature of most of the material on YouTube. Although the site does not allow nudity, there is a sufficient amount of content and provocative language. Teachers of younger students would be useful to consider this. Finally, some countries put bans on YouTube and other streaming video streams, which means that studies in these countries can face great difficulties when accessing useful online video.

Language is a significant aspect of the culture of the people and all over the countries, mankind has transmitted language from one generation to another, through the process of socialization. A child through association with the adults in the society learns language. Words are not neglected, but the boys and girls also study pictures and exhibits, work in a shop or laboratory, take school journeys, look at models, listen to radio programs and transcriptions, study slides and motion pictures.

To provide students with the ability to measure their own listening skills, We offered them regularly scheduled listening skills sessions, followed by regularly scheduled audio genre listening sessions. Have the students maintain a portfolio of their listening skills transcriptions, and genre predictions. After several exercises, have the students write and share their own self-evaluations of the ways in which their listening and genre skills have been enhanced.

We would recommend using video materials and modern alternative teaching approaches and methods to all the language teachers. It is important to have good class management skills and be able to inspire the pupils. The positive results will definitely delight both teachers and their students. During our work, we have found out that authentic materials play an important role in teaching a second language. They enrich the traditional lessons and are interesting for students, too. However, the pupils are not used to learning from alternative sources. They do not have much responsibility for their learning. In my opinion, they should be taught independence since early age.

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